

EU Health Literacy Atlas

DELIVERABLE D1.2

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¹ PU = Public
SEN = Sensitive

EU Health Literacy Atlas

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

Concept	Definition
Global Atlas of literacies for health GALH	It is a systematic collection of data and information that provides a visual and spatial representation of various features and aspects of a geographical area. The GALH is a tool that not only summarises the various literacy tools but presents the empirical evidence for how it has been used or evaluated in different geographical regions.
Health Literacy (HL)	HL entails people's knowledge and competences to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information to make judgments and decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention and health promotion ((1)
Digital HL (dHL)	dHL is the ability to seek, find, understand, and appraise health information from electronic sources and apply the knowledge gained to addressing or solving a health problem (2).
Literacies for Health	Literacies for Health in this Atlas refer to different types of HL such as nutritional HL, mental HL, oral HL, Physical Fitness Literacy, Medication Literacy, Environmental Health Literacy, Public Health Literacy, Reproductive Health Literacy, Genetic Literacy, Health Insurance Literacy, Occupational Health Literacy, Chronic Disease Management Literacy, among others. The literacies for health involve: Motivation, knowledge, and competencies to comprehend, evaluate, and apply information about health, thereby enabling the ability to make decisions in relation to personal care and disease prevention (3)
HL and/or digital HL levels	HL and digital HL levels refer to the level of HL of individuals or groups as measured by scales (measurement tools) developed for the purpose.
European Union	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden.
Beyond EU	Australia, Canada, New Zealand, United Kingdom (England, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales), United States of America.
Health Care/Health-care/Healthcare	Health care/Health-care/Healthcare exist in health system, that consists of all organisations, people, and actions whose primary intent is to promote, restore or maintain health. This includes efforts to influence determinants of health as well as more direct health-improving activities. A health system is therefore more than the pyramid of publicly owned facilities that deliver personal health services. It includes, for example, a mother caring for a sick child at home; private providers; behaviour change programmes; vector-control campaigns; health insurance organisations; occupational health and safety legislation. It includes cross-sectoral action by health staff, for example, encouraging the ministry of education to promote female education, a well-known determinant of better health (4)
Health Data	Health data is any data "related to health conditions, reproductive outcomes, causes of death, and quality of life"(5) for an individual or population. Health data includes clinical metrics along with environmental, socioeconomic, and

	behavioural information pertinent to health and wellness. A plurality of health data is collected and used when individuals interact with health care systems. This data, collected by health care providers, typically includes a record of services received, conditions of those services, and clinical outcomes or information concerning those services (6).
GALH Dataset	The GALH dataset is a collection of data related to levels, interventions, initiatives, practices and policy of (d)HL in Europe and beyond. The individual data points included are related to a specific (d)HL analysis of four different literature reviews. A dataset can contain various types of data, the GALH dataset contains numerical values and text that were extracted from the IDEAHL project literature reviews.
Social Innovation	Social innovation refers to the design and implementation of new solutions that imply conceptual, process, product, or organisational change, which ultimately aim to improve the welfare and wellbeing of individuals and communities. Many initiatives undertaken by the social economy and by the civil society have proven to be innovative in dealing with socio-economic and environmental problems, while contributing to economic development. To fully tap the potential of social innovation, an enabling policy framework is needed to support public, non-profit, and private actors to co-construct and implement socially innovative solutions and thereby contribute to address socio-economic issues, build stronger territorial resilience, and better respond to future shocks (7).
Social Services	Social service is a service that aims at promoting citizen's / client's social wellbeing and ability to function and prevents, reduces, and eliminates social problems (8).
Best practice	A best practice is a relevant policy or intervention implemented in a real-life setting and which has been favourably assessed in terms of adequacy (ethics and evidence) and equity as well as effectiveness and efficiency related to process and outcomes. Other criteria are important for a successful transferability of the practice such as a clear definition of the context, sustainability, cross-sectional, and participation of stakeholders (9).
Champions and survivors	<i>Champions</i> = Professionals, services, organisations, municipalities, regions, etc. that published a peer reviewed article in a scientific journal providing evidence of success with initiatives (best practices) in relation to (d)HL ie: the initiatives showed improvement of levels of HL with pre test and post test measurement <i>Survivors</i> = Professionals, services, organisations, municipalities, regions, etc. that were less successful with initiatives (best practices) in relation to (d)HL.
Initiative	In the context of (d)HL, an initiative refers to a specific program, project, or action undertaken with the aim of promoting or advancing health literacy. It involves a deliberate effort to improve individuals' knowledge, skills, and abilities to obtain, understand, and use health information and services effectively. (d) HL initiatives can take various forms, such as educational campaigns, community-based interventions, policy development, healthcare provider training, websites, apps, or the creation of health communication materials tailored to different populations. These initiatives often aim to

	address health disparities, empower individuals to make informed decisions about their health, and enhance their overall health outcomes. An initiative may or may not be published in scientific peer reviewed papers and could be led by public or private entities or individuals.
Monitoring and evaluation tools, scales, measures, methods, and frameworks	Monitoring and evaluation tools, methods, and frameworks in (d)HL that are validated and published in peer-reviewed journals; they measure/quantify individuals' (d)HL (9) and organisations' HL and (d)HL environments covering different target populations and services (e.g., the HLS-EU questionnaire, the eHL Assessment toolkit (eHLA) and the eHL Questionnaire (eHLQ), the M-POHL network action or the WHO HL Road Map).
Private and public initiatives and services	Private and public initiatives and services related to (d)HL regarding testing/assessing, monitoring, training, capability building, education, consulting, development, communication, intervention, care, support, peer support, or community action. A public intervention is one that is initiated, funded, or overseen by a government or public sector entity. It is typically aimed at addressing public needs or societal issues and is funded through public resources.: A private intervention is initiated, funded, or operated by private entities, such as industry, non-profit organisations, or individual practitioners

ABBREVIATIONS

KEY CONCEPTS	
HL	Health Literacy
dHL	Digital HL
(d)HL	HL and dHL
GALH	Global Atlas of Literacies for Health
(d)HL SCALES	
Ar-eHEALS	Arabic version of electronic HL scale
3-brief SQ	Three brief screening questions
BHLS	Three-item Brief HL Screen
BRIEF	Brief HL Screening Tool
CHAT	Conversational HL Assessment Tool
C & CHL scale/CCHL	Communicative and Critical HL scale
CHLT-30	Cancer HL Test
DHLI	Digital HL Instrument
DNT-15	Diabetes Numeracy Test 15
eHL	Electronic HL
eHEALS-carer	eHL Scale for Carers
eHEALS	Electronic HL scale
EHLS	Everyday Health Information Screening Tool
eHLA	eHL assessment toolkit
eHLQ	eHL Questionnaire
EMHL	Espailove.net Mental HL test for Spanish Adolescents

FCCHL	Functional, Communicative, and Critical HL questionnaire
G-HL	General HL scale
GROHL	Greek Oral HL measurement instrument
HALS	Health Activities Literacy Scale of NALS
HAS-A	HL Assessment Scale for Adolescents
HBP-HLS	High Blood Pressure-HL Scale
HELIA	HL Instrument for Adults
HK-LS	Hypertension Knowledge-Level Scale
HL-HC	HL items from the dimension of health care
HLQ	HL Questionnaire
HLQ-SK	HL Questionnaire Slovakia
HLS19 -Q12	General HL adapted short form
HLS19-DIGI	General HL module for digital health literacy
HLS19-VAC	General HL module for vaccination health literacy
HLSAC	HL for School-aged Children
HLS-EU (Q6/Q16/Q25/Q47/Q86)	European HL Survey Questionnaire (nr. of questions in the questionnaires)
ILS-PT	HL Survey – Portugal
IMETER	Italian Medical Term Recognition Test
MAKS	Mental Health Knowledge Schedule
MeHLA	Danish Mental HL Adolescents questionnaire
METER	Medical Term Recognition Test
MHFA	Mental Health First Aid
MHKQ	Mental Health Knowledge Questionnaire
MHLq	Mental HL Questionnaire
MHLS	Mental HL Scale
MHLW	Mental HL tool for the Workplace
MHPK-10	Mental Health-Promoting Knowledge
MMHLM	Multicomponent mental HL measure
MOHLAA-Q	Measurement of HL Among Adolescents Questionnaire
NVS	Newest Vital Sign
NVS-PTeen	Newest Vital Sign for Portuguese Adolescents
OHP	Oral HL Profile
QUICK-K	An Instrument for Measuring HL in Children
RALPH	Recognizing and Addressing Limited Pharmaceutical literacy
REALM	Rapid Estimate of Adult Literacy in Medicine
REALM-R	Rapid Estimate of Adult Literacy in Medicine Revised
REALD-30	Rapid Estimate of Adult Literacy in Dentistry
SAHL-D	Short Assessment of HL for Dutch Patients
SAHLPA	Short Assessment of HL in Portugal
SAHL-PT	Short Assessment of HL for Portuguese population
SAHLSA-50	Short Assessment of HL for Spanish-Speaking Adults
SBSQ	Set of Brief Screening Questions
S-CCHL	Swedish Communicative and Critical HL Scale

S-FHL	Scale for Functional HL
SILS	Single Item Screener
S-TOFHLA	Abbreviated version of the Test of Functional HL in Adults
TOFHLA	Test of Functional HL in Adults
V-HLO	Vienna health literate organisation self-assessment tool
IDEAHL CONSORTIUM	
MDU	Mälardalen University
SeAMK	Seinäjäki University of Applied Sciences
UCN	University College of Northern Denmark
RMIT University	RMIT University
RMIT University, Europe	RMIT Europe
CSPA	Consejería de Salud y Servicios Sanitarios - Principado de Asturias
CE	Consulta Europa
ISRAA	Istituto per Servizi di Ricovero e Assistenza agli Anziani
MLHSA	Behörde fuer Arbeit, Gesundheit, Soziales, Familie Und Integration Hamburg
ADIPER	Adi & Salu Sersoc S.L.U.
CDC	Cáritas Diocesana de Coimbra
EIWH	European Institute of Women's Health Company Limited By Guarantee
CEI	Ince Iniziativa Centro Europea - Segretariato Esecutivo
E-seniors	E-Seniors: Initiation des Seniors aux NTICc Association
All Digital	All Digital Aisbl
General acronyms	
BMI	Body Mass Index
EHL	Environmental HL
EU	European Union
FHL	Functional HL
mHL	Mental HL
OHL	Organisational HL
oHL	Oral HL
PTHL	Pharmacotherapy Literacy
WHO	World Health Organization
Yr.	Years(s)
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
MHFA	Mental Health First Aid
USA	United States of America
UK	United Kingdom
RCT	Randomized controlled trial
Chi ²	Chi-Square
DF	Degrees of freedom
CFI	Comparative fit index
TLI	Tucker-Lewis Index
RMSEA	The root mean square error of approximation
WLSMV	Weighted least square mean and variance adjusted
SD	Standard Deviation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Global Atlas of Literacies for Health (GALH) of the IDEAHL project is an online visualisation tool for teaching, research, practice and policy making in health care.

The GALH is a resource that not only summarises the various **literacy instruments** (10) used but presents the empirical evidence for how the tools have been used or evaluated and the best practices in (digital) health literacy ((d)LH) across Europe and beyond. The GALH was developed and managed by the Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology (RMIT) and RMIT University (RMIT-Uni) based on the results of the Work Package 1 (WP1) of the European Union-funded Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL, <https://ideahl.eu/>) that has received funding by the Horizon Europe Framework Program under GA 101057477 (11).

To be more specific, **the Atlas is:**

- An online data visualisation tool that shows the levels of (d)HL, practice, policy, interventions, initiatives and EU projects in Europe and beyond.
- A comprehensive resource for (d)HL policymaking in the EU.
- A tool for enhancing teaching, research, practice and policy in health care.
- A resource for promoting health equity and digital empowerment in the EU and beyond.

The Atlas of the IDEAHL project was developed to visually present the data from different (d)HL scales on an interactive map and datatable and practice, policy, interventions and initiatives data in datatables. Users can filter data by population: adult, child and adolescence, health workforce, or select to present only country or region level data or download the datasets to perform their own analysis and customized data visualization.

The GAHL answers the IDEAHL consortium's objective to design and implement an Atlas that provides a repository for (d)HL research article data and practice, policies, interventions, EU funded projects and initiatives. This will support data exploration of the evidence and practice/policy information, allowing users to better understand (d)HL across Europe and Beyond.

The entire development of the GALH of the IDEAHL project **is based on the results of the literature reviews** of task 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3 of WP1 of the IDEAHL project and was implemented in three phases:

- 1) Consortium collaborative literatures reviews to address task 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 of WP1. In this phase the information sources for the development of the Atlas were selected
- 2) Integration of reviews and data extraction (task 1.4a)
- 3) Interactive map: app, datatables and website (task 1.4b).

As a result of this process, 68 peer reviewed scientific studies focusing on interventions published in Europe and Beyond (11) and 21 peer reviewed scientific studies addressing best practice (of which successful best practices =champions; n: 15) published between 2017 and 2023 from Europe and Beyond were included in the Atlas. Moreover, 163 peer reviewed scientific studies focusing on scales and monitoring of (d)HL focusing in the European Union published between 2018 and 2022 (11) were included in the Atlas. Finally, 148 initiatives and European Projects from an ad-hoc supplementary review of which 107 (72%) refer to Spain and 48 (28%) to EU countries were included in the Atlas.

The GALH of the IDEAHL project **was co-created and co-designed in workshops** with (d)HLEuropean experts, representatives of patient and carers associations, academics and educators in biomedical sciences, digital health/med-tech professionals, geospatial experts and social scientists. After the dataextraction process of the articles included, the GALH datasets are composed of 653 records and 77 variables. Regarding monitoring of (d)HL levels through scales 75,6% of the records refer to health literacy, 23,8% to digital health literacy and 3,1% refer to both literacies. Regarding practice and policy data (including initiatives, interventions, projects and grey literature publications) the records show 21 evidence based best practices published in scientific peer reviewed papers. 15 of these practices were categorized as *champions* by the IDEAHL Consortium as they were considered as successful best practices (i.e: they showed improvement of HL after the interventions).

The co-design of the Atlas **was in consultation with the IDEAHL consortium and with a panel of 20 health literacy and digital health literacy experts from across Europe**. The panel participated in three workshops with RMIT and RMIT Uni to co-design the appearance and function of the Atlas, including the most important information they want to view when entering the Atlas and subsequent information they want to view and extract. Overwhelming, the experts reported the literacy levels mapped across Europe was the most important piece of information they first wanted to view in the Atlas. Next, they want to compare country level data. Both of these have been achieved by launching the Atlas on the interactive map screen, where the user can select

which literacy they wish to review. As each tool to measure literacy differs in topics and scoring, it is not possible to view the literacy level without selecting a specific tool, so the Atlas website provides information about the different scales. Experts then want to be able to do a deeper dive on the literacy data. As such, the Atlas allows the user to move to the raw data whilst maintaining the filters they selected on the interactive map. In the data table, they can select relevant articles to view high level summary data from that article and a link to the article. Lastly, experts wanted to view the best practice and policy resources for different countries, which is available in high level data table format with web links to the relevant resources.

The Atlas is an **open access**, free of charge resource and it will be accessible for academics, educators, policy makers and the general public with interest in (d)HL levels and initiatives in European countries via:

- Link to the Atlas (during the life of the IDEAHL project and beyond): [GALH: Global Atlas of Literacies for Health](#)
- The website of the project IDEAHL (during the life of the IDEAHL project): <https://ideahl.eu/>
- A web browser at RMIT's website (during the life of the IDEAHL project and beyond): <https://www.rmit.eu/galh>

1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this deliverable is to explain the process for the development of the Global Atlas of Literacies for Health (GALH) which is a comprehensive and accessible tool that summarizes the studies and practice around (digital) health literacy ((d)HL) in various contexts. The Atlas aims to facilitate learning and understanding of the levels of (d)HL necessary to fully participate in today's society.

General objective of the GALH

The GALH answers the IDEAHL consortium's objective to design and implement an atlas that provides a repository for d(HL) research article data and best practice, policy, interventions and initiatives data. This will support data exploration of the evidence and best practice information, allowing users to better understand (d)HL across Europe and Beyond.

Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of GALH of the IDEAHL project are to:

1. **Collect and organize scientific resources:** to gather a wide range of scientific resources related to monitoring, interventions and best practices in (digital) health literacy.
2. **Offer an intuitive and accessible structure:** design a clear and user-friendly structure within the Atlas. This involves creating intuitive navigation and content presentation that allows users to quickly find relevant information tailored to their specific needs.
3. **Provide content tailored to different skill levels:** ensure that the Atlas offers content tailored to different levels of end users. This will enable users, from general public and patients to practitioners, academia and policy makers, to find relevant and challenging material that helps them improve teaching, practice and policy making around (digital) health literacy.
4. **Foster participation and collaboration:** promote active participation of the community in the development of the Atlas. Collaboration with digital literacy experts, educators, and users will be encouraged to ensure that the content and functionalities of the Atlas are relevant, up-to-date, and responsive to the changing needs of users.

5. **Continuously evaluate and improve the Atlas:** establish a process of continuous evaluation and improvement of the Atlas. User feedback will be collected, and up to six regular updates are planned to ensure that the Atlas remains an effective and updated tool in the field of (d)HL by the end of the project.

Out of scope

During the development of the interactive scales map app and data repository for the GALH , the consortium has established these items as out of scope:

1. Support of a changed data structure in provided Atlas data.
2. Quality Assurance of provided Atlas data.
3. Inclusion of data not provided as part of task 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3.
4. Self-service data management. Any data updates are to be provided to technical team to process and release.
5. System usage statistics, either self-service (e.g., via Google analytics), or via request to the Atlas App management team. System usage statistics will be available via google analytics of RMIT Europe website.
6. Extensive mobile phone (small user interface) design and testing.
7. Helpdesk/support for ad-hoc queries on the Atlas use or statistics.

2. METHODOLOGY

The GALH is developed in the methodological and conceptual framework and within the IDEAHL's projects objectives. Three different phases have been structured for the development of the GALH:

Phase 1: Results of the literature review (Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3)

Phase 2: Integrations of reviews, data extraction and qualification of findings

Phase 3: Interactive map

The three phases, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Three phases of the development of GALH of the IDEAHL project

These three methodological phases will be described in detail below:

PHASE 1: LITERATURE REVIEW

The data available in the GALH comes from the results of the WP 1 (Map (d)HL research and practices in Europe and beyond) already described in deliverable D.1.1 (Report on (d)HL) (11).

The data extraction process was conducted from the results of IDEAHL project WP1, regarding (d)HL analysis of research and practices in Europe and beyond. The information sources of the GALH include the following categories:

- **Evidence of monitoring levels (scales) of digital health literacy (dHL) and health literacy:** country, population, scale, first author, country coverage, HL or dHL, reference, note (summary of the study) and link to read the full text.
- **Practice, policy, interventions, projects and initiatives:** country, year, title, lead organisation, status, international/national/regional, public or private, type (report, book, dissertation, project, website, etc.), HL, dHL, other, age group, target group, level (individual, family, community, group, society, organisational), sector (academia, education, industry, public health), tool or scale, champion/survivor, reference, note.

The description of these categories is shown in Annex 1, under the name Data Dictionary.

PHASE 2: INTEGRATION OF REVIEWS, DATA EXTRACTION AND QUALIFICATION OF FINDINGS

The integration of reviews consists of:

- (a) a data extraction process,
- (b) curation, consistency and cleaning of data,
- (c) Collaborative analysis of the data with dHL and geospatial experts,
- (d) Co-creation, co-design and qualification of findings workshops with dHL an dHL European Experts.

A. Data extraction process

In this phase two datasets were developed through the extraction of data from phase 1 results (11). A dataset related to the monitoring and measurement scales of health literacy, and another dataset of the Practice and Policy related to d(HL)

Table 1 shows the relationship with the tasks of WP1, as well as the studies included for the data extraction that integrate the GALH dataset.

IDEAHL WP1 Task	Number of Studies	Inclusion in Dataset
Task 1.1 Map and analysis of the existing (d)HL literature related to intervention in the EU and beyond	68 peer reviewed scientific studies published in Europe and Beyond	GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA (only if numeric value levels of dHL were reported) GALH dataset2 Repository of Practice/Policy DATA
Task 1.2 Map and analysis of Best practice to improve (d) HL	21 peer reviewed scientific (of which successful best practices =champions; n: 15) published in Europe and Beyond	GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA (only if numeric value levels of dHL were reported) GALH dataset2 Repository of Practice/Policy DATA (only if no levels of dHL and HL were reported)
Task 1.3 Map and analysis of approaches to monitor and assess (d)HL	163 peer reviewed scientific studies published between 2018 and 2022 in the EU	GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA
Ad hoc review of practice, policy, projects and initiatives	148 initiatives and European Projects of which 107 (72%) refer to Spain and 48 (28%) to EU countries.	GALH dataset2 Repository of Practice/Policy DATA

Table 1 Data extraction related to included studies in literatures reviews of IDEAHL WP1

After delimiting the corpus of studies and initiatives, each one was linked to records in two separate databases, based on the type of data that could be extracted and the type of variables

that could be established, such as string, categorical, or numerical variables (Table 2) A total of 653 records and 77 variables were established in the GALH datasets.

To clarify, the process of data extraction from research articles (studies), grey literature and other information sources included an analysis of the type of information available per country. As an example, one study can have information about one country or more, one scale or more, one population or more. That is why the GALH doesn't count articles per country but *records of information* per country. For example, if one study reports (d)HL of 5 countries comparing two different scales for the same population, we would have Number of studies: 1, Number of records: 5, number of variables: 2 (1x5x3). The variables in this case are the 2 scales and the population.

IDEAHL Dataset	GALH	Data extracted from Workpackage 1	Number of studies	Number of records	Number of variables
GALH dataset 1 Monitoring dataset		- Task 1.3	163 peer reviewed scientific studies published between 2018 and 2022 in the EU.(11)	193	53
GALH dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA		- Task 1.1, Task 1.2 - Supplementary Ad hoc review of practice, policy and initiatives	68 (11) + 21 peer reviewed scientific studies (of which successful best practices =champions; n: 15) published in Europe and Beyond (11) + 148 initiatives and European Projects of which 107 (72%) refer to Spain and 48 (28%) to EU countries.	460	24
Total		Task 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3	252 peer reviewed scientific studies +	653	77

	Supplementary Ad hoc review of practice, policy and initiatives	148 initiatives, projects policy, practice and interventions.		
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Table 2: Records and variables of GALH datasets

B. Datasets consolidation: curation, consistency and cleaning of data

GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA

Is composed of 163 peer reviewed scientific studies published between 2018 and 2022 in the EU and (11) and has 53 variables to address the objectives of the IDEAHL project (12). The established variables were the literacy scales (13) together with filter variables such as target population and country. A variable is an identifier that represents a value and acts as a container to hold a particular piece of data (14). To be able to develop an interactive map a numeric value range was established in each of the numeric variables (a minimum and maximum value range). The value ranges are the ones reported by the author of the studies as the level of (d)HL of the target populations that were studied (the values are shown exactly as reported by the authors of studies. Reviewing the task 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3, 163 peer reviewed scientific studies, 68 peer reviewed scientific studies published in Europe and Beyond (11), 21 best practice studies (of which successful best practices =champions; n: 15). 193 records were able to be included in the GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA .

This means that all these 193 records reported levels of (d) HL and can be clearly be assigned to a numeric value range in one of the numeric variable (table3).

For the purpose of consistency and cleaning of the data the 252 scientific studies included in the corpus were reviewed.

As a result of this process a variable was inserted in the dataset referring to the limitations of the studies that were conducted mentioning whether the reported level of (d)HL had limited or good country coverage.

DIMENSION	VARIABLE NAME	DEFINITION	TYPE AND CATEGORY
id	Artice #	article number id	numeric
id	First author	First author last name	open text
id	country	name of EU country	name of each Who EU country

Target population	population	target groups mentioned in the studies based on analysis guide task 1.3	nominal / general adult population, children and adolescents, patients, health workforce
Leves of d HL	measures	the name of the measures used in each study	numeric, the value of dHL informed in each study (/100, /5, score, etc)
Methodology	Note	Description of characteristics of target population mentioned, sample size, dHL levels and validation of measures (as indicated in country reports task 1.3)	open text / string
id	reference	NLM/Vancouver reference title	open text /string
Methodology	Coverage	Country coverage of the study	nominal / limited, good
Measurement	BRIEF	Brief HL Screening Tool	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	BRIEF	Brief HL Screening Tool	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	CHLT-30 PT	Communicative and Critical HL scale	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	CSQ	Communicative and Critical HL scale	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	D/lit	Depression mental heath literacy	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	DHLI	Digital HL Instrument	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	eHEALS	Electronic HL scale	numeric value range reported in included study

Measurement	eHEALS Carer	eHL Scale for Carers	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	eHL	Electronical HL	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	eHLA	eHL assessment toolkit	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	eHLQ	eHL Questionnaire	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	EHML	Espailove.net Mental HL test for Spanish Adolescents	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	FCCHL	Functional, Communicative, and Critical HL questionnaire	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	GROHL	Greek Oral HL measurement instrument	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HIL	Health literacy instrument	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HL55item/EDUFI	Health literacy survey EDUFY	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLQ	Health literacy questionnaire	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLQ Scale 1-5	Health literacy questionnaire	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLQ scale 6-9	Health literacy questionnaire	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLS-EU-Child-Q15	European HL Survey Questionnaire (nr. of questions in the questionnaires)	numeric value range reported in included study

Measurement	HLS-EU-Q16	European HL Survey Questionnaire (nr. of questions in the questionnaires)	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLS-EU-Q47	European HL Survey Questionnaire (nr. of questions in the questionnaires)	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLS-EU-Q6	European HL Survey Questionnaire (nr. of questions in the questionnaires)	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLS19-DIGI	European HL Survey Questionnaire (dHL)	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLS19-Q12	European HL Survey Questionnaire (nr. of questions in the questionnaires)	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLS19-VAC	European HL Survey Questionnaire (Vaccination HL)	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	HLSAC	HL for School-aged Children	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	IMETER	Italian Medical Term Recognition Test	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	MHL	Mental Health literacy	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	NVS	Newest Vital Sign	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	NVS Pteen	Newest Vital Sign for Portuguese Adolescents	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	OHL	Oral HL	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	RALPH	Recognizing and Addressing Limited Pharmaceutical literacy	numeric value range reported in included study

Measurement	READHY	Readiness and Enablement Index for Health Technology	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	REALD-30	Rapid Estimate of Adult Literacy in Dentistry	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	REALM-SF	Rapid Estimate of Adult Literacy in Medicine Revised	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	S-TOFHLA	Abbreviated version of the Test of Functional HL in Adults	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	SAHL-D	Short Assessment of HL for Dutch Patients	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	SAHL/PT	Short Assessment of HL in Portugal	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	SAHLPA-23	Short Assessment of HL in Portuga (n of questions)l	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	SALSHA_50	Short Assessment of HL for Spanish-Speaking Adults	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	SCCHL	Swedish Communicative and Critical HL Scale	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	SILS	Single Item Screener	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	Swedish C & CHL	Swedish Communicative and Critical HL Scale	numeric value range reported in included study
Measurement	Swedish FHL Scale	Swedish Functional Health Literacy Scale	numeric value range reported in included study

Table 3. GALH Dataset1: Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA

GALH dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA

Is composed of 68 + 21 peer reviewed scientific studies (of which successful best practices =champions; n: 15) published in Europe and Beyond and has 24 variables. It also is composed of 148 initiatives, projects, policy, practice and interventions. 460 records were able to be included in this dataset mainly in text type nominal-categorical variables (Table 4). The records in this dataset were reviewed by 16 (d)HL experts after the co-creation and co-design workshops who were able to include include missing data and complement the ad-hoc supplementary review with more information sources.

After the co-creation workshop an online form was designed to allowed end users to report missing data. This form will be published in the GALH website.

DIMENSION	VARIABLE NAME	DEFINITION	TYPE ANDCATEGORIES
id	Article #	article number id (for internal use)	numeric
id	Country	name of EU and Beyond country	categorical,name of each country
id	Title	Title of the record	open text, string
id	Lead Organisation	name of lead organization	open text, string
id	First author	First author last name	open text, string
id	Other authors	Other authos last name	numeric, year
id	Year (start)	Beginning date of initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc.	numeric, year
id	Year (last)	End date of initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	numeric, year
id	Status	Status of the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, ongoing, finished, published
id	Hyperlink local language	website of of the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	open text, string
id	Hyperlink English	english language website of the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	open text, string

id	DOI	Digital object identifier number	open text, string
id	Category	Category of HL address by the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, dHL, HL, other
id	Jurisdiction	jurisdiction of the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, national, regional, other
id	Visibility	access and visibility of the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, public, private, other
methodology	Type	type of initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, health plan, project, blog post, instagram channell, efectiviness study, systematic review, review, etc.
methodology	Age group	age group of the population addressed by the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, children, adolescents, adults, general
methodology	Target group	target group of the population addressed by the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, Citizens, Health workforce , Health system, other
id	Level	level of the population addressed by the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	categorical, organizational, poblational, individual, group
id	Sector	sector of initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc	open text, string
methodology	Tool or Measure	name of scale measurement usde by the inititative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc.	open text, string
id	Champion / Survivor	Succesful intervention in dHL or HL	categorical, champion
id	Reference	Bibliographic reference	open text, string

id	Note	Brief description of the initiative, intervention, policy, practice, project, etc.	open text, string
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Table 4 GALH dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA

C. Collaborative analysis of the data with dHL and geospatial experts

Both GALH datasets were analysed in terms of their possibility of visualization of data in interactive maps. After a review of the geospatial experts it was stated that:

It is possible to map scale measurements as the choropleth visualises which countries have lower values and which have higher values in the established measurement ranges.

The inclusion criteria, then, for the interactive map is related to the possibility of establishment of a value range level (table 5). This numeric value levels were reported in the studies included in the corpus. The measurement levels were developed in an interactive map and provide comparative information about the state of the measurement of the countries.

IDEAHL WP1 Task	Number of Studies	Inclusion in Dataset	Interactive map
Task 1.1 Map and analysis of the existing (d)HL literature related to intervention in the EU and beyond	68 studies published in Europe and Beyond (11)	GALH dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA Partially in GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA	Only the studies that report measurement levels were able to be established are shown in the interactive map. It is possible to map scale measurements as the choropleth visualises which countries have lower values, which have higher values in the established ranges.

Task 1.2 Map and analysis of Best practice to improve (d) HL	21 (of which successful best practices =champions; n: 15) published in Europe and Beyond (11)	GALH dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA Partially in GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA	Only the studies that report measurement levels were able to be established are shown in the interactive map. It is possible to map scale measurements as the choropleth visualises which countries have lower values, which have higher values in the established ranges.
Task 1.3 Map and analysis of approaches to monitor and assess (d)HL	163 studies published between 2018 and 2022 in the EU.(11)	GALH Dataset1 Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA Partially in GALH Dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA	The data extracted from this information sources were able to visualize in the interactive map as value ranges were able to be established. It is possible to map scale measurements as the choropleth visualises which countries have lower values, which have higher values in the established ranges.
Supplementary Ad hoc review of practice, policy and initiatives	148 initiatives and European Projects of which 107 (72%) refer to Spain and 48 (28%) to EU countries.	GALH dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA	No value ranges were able to be established

Table 5. Inclusion in interactive map

D. Co-creation, co-design and qualification of findings workshops with HL and dHL European Experts.

The development of the Atlas was conceived as a tool intended to be useful for various stakeholders. For this reason, each stage of development underwent three testing iterations through co-creation and co-design workshops of qualification of findings (figure 1) with twenty (20) experts in health literacy, digital health literacy, and participants from the network of champions of the IDEAHL project (Table 6). The experts that participated in the workshops were not only selected from universities or academia. The experts were members of the European Health Connected Alliance (ECHAlliance), including government, health & social care providers, researchers, the network of champions of the IDEAHL project, and representatives of patients' associations. The experts came from different countries and regions in the WHO European Union. The specific areas of expertise of the participants related to (d)HL were Health Psychology, Pharmacy, Gerontology, policy and effectiveness related to health , women in global health, health technology assessment and digital health and social affairs. The significance of co-creation in such projects is noteworthy, as it fosters collaborative input and ensures that diverse perspectives and expertise are integrated into the final product.

Workshop dates	Number of participants	Target Group
Ws 1. 2/5/2023	16	HL and dHL Experts + network of champions
Ws 2. 30/5/2023	20	HL and dHL Experts + network of champions
Ws 3. 17/7/2023	20	HL and dHL Experts + network of champions

Table 6. Workshops with dHL and Digital Health Experts.

The first two workshops (figure 2), focus on the conceptual framework of the Atlas and dHL and Digital Health Experts reflected on this main questions:

- What is the first thing they want to look at in the Atlas
- What other questions do you want the Atlas to answer?,
- How do you think each of these roles would use the Atlas: healthcare provider, health manager, policy maker, academic/researcher/educator, students?

- What high level summary data do you want to see on the about page?

The feedback received from a panel of dHL and digital health experts about the GALH being developed provided insights into their information preferences. Overwhelming, **the experts reported the literacy levels mapped across Europe was the most important piece of information they first wanted to view in the Atlas.** Next, they want to compare country level data. Both of these have been achieved by launching the Atlas on the interactive map screen, where the user can select which literacy they wish to review. As each tool to measure literacy differs in topics and scoring, it is not possible to view the literacy level without selecting a specific tool, so the Atlas website provides information about the different scales. They emphasized the importance of examining the disparities in (d)HL within countries, seeking recommendations regarding the tools utilized. They also expressed interest in having access to the current dHL measures (scales) specific to each country, enabling effective comparisons between nations. Additionally, they highlighted the need for identifying geographical areas with limited information on (d)HL, signaling the necessity for further research in these regions. The experts also expressed the need to facilitate comparisons of different countries within specific regions, such as South East Europe. Furthermore, they stressed the significance of the GALH making a real contribution to existing resources in the field. Insights into what hasn't worked in the past and understanding the reasons behind it were also requested. The experts expressed their interest in comprehending how the measurement is functioning in each country to ensure its practical efficacy. The dHL and digital health experts expressed they they found the systematization of measurements and the possibility of benchmarking scales between countries as a valuable resource for research, policy, practice and education. Experts then want to be able to do a deeper dive on the literacy data. As such, the Atlas allows the user to move to the raw data whilst maintaining the filters they selected on the interactive map. In the data table, they can select relevant articles to view high level summary data from that article and a link to the article. Lastly, experts wanted to view the best practice and policy resources for different countries, which is available in high level.

During the workshops, one of the key discussions revolved around the value of incorporating not only an interactive map but also a data table into the Atlas. The participants acknowledged that providing users with the ability to perform their own analyses and create graphs for visualization would greatly enhance the Atlas's usability and effectiveness.

Various aspects related to the quality assessment of individual studies and non-standardized measures were addressed during the workshops. Additionally, there was a focus on establishing links to validation studies for different scales used in the Atlas. The experts also emphasized the importance of considering inequities between countries, incorporating some form of uncertainty measure, and providing standard deviations and margins of error for the measurements. Furthermore, they highlighted the significance of including the date of measurement (e.g., year) and assessing the quality and evidence of the studies incorporated into the Atlas.

Looking toward future developments, the (d) HL and digital health experts expressed interest in gaining insights into whether the results of the studies had been applied and used in health policies. They suggested that feeding the Atlas with national health data for comparison with digital health literacy measurements (dHL) and also live data from surveys and studies would be valuable. Additionally, they raised the need to explore rural versus urban differences and the level of infrastructure and digital support available in each country, as these factors can significantly impact (d)HL outcomes. By considering these suggestions, the Atlas can evolve into a more comprehensive and impactful tool for health literacy research and intervention efforts.

During the co-creation and co-design workshops, mock-up images of the website were distributed to gather feedback and insights. Following this, the map was presented to consortium partners, and a dedicated workshop involving (d) HL and digital health experts, consortium partners and the network of champions of the IDEAHL project was finally conducted. This workshop served to thoroughly test and analyze the website, aiming to qualify and validate the findings based on the experts valuable input and expertise.

Figure 2. Flyers of invitation to the workshops and testing of the GALH of the IDEAHL project

PHASE 3: INTERACTIVE MAP (WEBSITE)

In this phase, geospatial experts developed an interactive map for the visualization of the findings. As explained before, the interactive map includes the **GALHdataset 1 (monitoring and scale levels)**.

Scales refer to monitoring and evaluation tools, methods, and frameworks in (d)HL that are validated and published in peer-reviewed journals; they measure/quantify individuals' (d)HL and organisations' HL and (d)HL environments covering different target populations and services (e.g., the HLS-EU questionnaire, the eHL Assessment toolkit -eHLA- and the eHL Questionnaire -eHLQ-, HLQ, BRIEF, etc). A health literacy scale is a standardised questionnaire or survey designed to capture various aspects of health literacy, such as the ability to understand and use health information, navigate healthcare systems, and make informed decisions about health. These scales typically consist of a series of questions or statements that respondents rate or answer to, providing quantitative data on their health literacy abilities. Health literacy scales are valuable in research, evaluation, and intervention efforts, helping to identify gaps, track progress and tailor interventions to improve health literacy and promote better health outcomes.

The GALH compiles different types of scales that measure (d)HL and are shown in an interactive map. To see a complete description of the scale and how it is implemented the GALH allows end users to either see the reference or read the full text via a link to where it was published. Health literacy scales play a crucial role in research, evaluation, and intervention endeavors, as they are instrumental in pinpointing disparities, monitoring advancements, and customizing interventions to enhance health literacy and foster improved health outcomes (15, 16, 17).

The interactive map allows to easy visualize the gaps in research and the need to support some countries more than others in developing this area of knowledge that is correlated to improvement of health outcomes and behaviors (15, 16, 17)

The GALH is a map supported in the Google Maps Platform that was developed specially by geospatial experts for the IDEAHL project. It is set up in an RMIT Europe Google Cloud project (18).

Google Maps is an online map platform that offers a different features (18). The map is secured by a unique API (Application Programming Interface) code that allows the incorporation and customization of the google map with the IDEAHL's data (18). By restricting API calls only to

authorized people (the developer of the GALH) the map is secured from unauthorized use and the data is protected (18).

As being set up in a google map, the GALH uses WGS84 standard reference system (18). WGS84 uses a three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system to define positions on the Earth (18). It consists of latitude (measured in degrees north or south of the equator), longitude (measured in degrees east or west of the Prime Meridian), and ellipsoidal height (measured above or below the reference ellipsoid) (18). WGS84 is adopted and used as the standard geodetic reference system for various applications, including mapping, navigation, surveying, and global positioning systems (GPS) (18). The original atlas of the IDEAHL project was planned to be developed in NUTS (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) a classification system used by the European Union (EU) for dividing regions within its member states. As the collected data in WP1 included monitoring, practices and interventions from Europe and Beyond, it was necessary to adopt the google maps standard so that all the information could be visualized properly.

Googlemap allows to upload, store, and manage data to the Google Cloud Console, to use it with Google Maps Platform APIs (18). For this:

- 1) a Google Cloud Project account has been set up to to start using the platform and
- 2) The monitoring dataset was integrated and uploaded in order visualize the data.

There are some technical prerequisites established by google to upload a dataset that are steted in their documentation information centre (18), such as the supported file types that can only be CSV, GeoJSON, or KML of maximum size of 350 MB. The CSV files uploaded followed those prerequisites having in the column names h priority of order of this dimensions: latitude, longitude -lat, long- x, y- wkt (Well-Known Text representation of geometry).

Basically, the **GALH of the IDEAHL project works as any Google Maps**. This has the advantage that it is a very well-known tool so it will be very easy to be used and understandable for end-users. No technical expertise is needed to use the GALH as it is similar to any goolge map that shows detailed maps of different regions and places around the world. It is possible to navigate and focus in or out on the map to gather information about one particular country.

The Platform is secured from unauthorized use by restricting API calls to those that provide proper authentication credentials. The decision to use the Google maps plataform is also based on the the usability possibilities and the fact that this tool has been increasly used in health care

and public health for epidemiological data and social determinants of health (18). Whilst it is acknowledge that no personal identifiable data is collected in this project, in the event that for the provision of the Services described with this platform, the Service Provider does accesses and process personal data on behalf of the project, they will be notified and shall do so in the capacity of data processor, fulfilling the obligations according to the Regulation EU 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data (the “GDPR”), and the Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights, (the LOPDGDD), and its modification Law 11/2023, of May 8th.

3. RESULTS

The GALH site has this structure and layers:

- Landing page: GAHL, FAQs and Get in Touch
- Child page: Glossary
- Child page: Datadictionary

The general information in Land page is showed in Annex 4.

3.1 GAHL

The main result of the GALH is the website where an interactive map of measurement levels of (d)HL and two downloadable datatables with scales and practice/policy data.

The Atlas is an **open access**, free of charge resource and it will be accessible for academics, educators, policy makers and the general public with interest in (d)HL levels and initiatives in European countries via:

- Link to the Atlas (during the life of the IDEAHL project and beyond): [GALH: Global Atlas of Literacies for Health](#)
- The website of the project IDEAHL (during the life of the IDEAHL project): <https://ideahl.eu/>
- A web browser at RMIT's website (during the life of the IDEAHL project and beyond): <https://www.rmit.eu/galh>

It is important to clarify that the 252 peer reviewed scientific studies and 148 initiatives, EU funded projects policy, practice and interventions included in the GALH lead to 653 records in both datasets.

This is due to the fact that one study could have information about 1 or more countries or 1 or more scales. In the next section we present a summary of the data included in the GALH for geographical online visualization (interactive and in datatable and graphics format).

Data per country was included in the MONITORING OF LEVELS OF (d)HL AND HL SCALES INCLUDED IN THE galh AS A RESULT OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW OF WP1 OF THE IDEAHL PROJECT

GALH includes data from a wide range of countries, primarily from Europe and mainly from Germany, Italy, Portugal and Denmark, as shown in the tables below.

Country	dHL/HL scale level record count
Germany	28
Italy	17
Portugal	16
Denmark	16
Ireland	11
Spain	10
Hungary	10
Netherlands	8
France	8
Sweden	7
Poland	7
Belgium	7
Austria	7
Slovakia	6
USA	5
Greece	5
Finland	5
Czechia	5
Romania	3
Norway	3
Bulgaria	3
Australia	2
Slovenia	1
England	1
Cyprus	1
Croatia	1

Table 7. GALH of the IDEAHL project monitoring scale levels data per country. Europe and Beyond (record count)

Most of the studies have adults as their target population (58,5%). 24,8% refer to patients and 10,3% to children and adolescents. Only 6,2% focused on the levels of (d)HL of the healthcare workforce (table 8).

Country	health workforce	children and adolescents	patients	general adult population	dHL/HL scale level record count	
Germany		3	4	6	15	28
Italy		3	1	5	8	17
Portugal			1	5	10	16
Denmark		1	1	5	9	16
Ireland		1		4	6	11
Spain			1	3	6	10
Hungary					10	10
Netherlands		1	2	3	2	8
France				4	4	8
Sweden			1	2	4	7
Poland			2	1	4	7
Belgium			1	1	5	7
Austria			2		5	7
Slovakia			1		5	6
USA				3	2	5
Greece		2		1	2	5
Finland			3		2	5
Czechia				1	4	5
Romania				1	2	3
Norway					3	3
Bulgaria					3	3
Australia				2		2
Slovenia					1	1
England					1	1
Cyprus		1				1
Croatia				1		1
						0
total	12	20	48	113	193	

Table 8. GALH of the IDEAHL project monitoring scale levels data per country and target population. Europe and Beyond (record count)

There are 39 countries from Europe and Beyond that are included in the practice/policy dataset of the GALH so that it is possible to access a data table that allows end users to perform their own analysis.

According to the results of WP1 of the IDEAHL project:

“There is great heterogeneity in interventions improving one or more outcomes related to (d)HL, health, access to information and behaviour or procedures and policies (...) Core tendencies in this field of research include interventions aiming at training health care professionals, patients, caregivers, or others.

It has been difficult to conclude on best practices as the effect of most interventions was not using well established evaluation methods, still, the most applied interventions were education and training and testing and revising information materials. In many interventions technologies were important elements. More research is needed to determine best practice”. (11)

The type of practice, policy, interventions, projects and initiatives included are mainly Horizon 2020 projects, health plans, programs or strategies, books (ebooks, book chapters), websites, apps and digital newsletters, studies (effectiveness, mixed methods, randomized controlled trials), reports, policy briefs and articles (systematic reviews, reviews, scoping reviews) as shown in table 9.

Type of pract	Total %
Horizon 2020 project:	24.6
Health Plan, Program, Strategy	19.2
Report:	8.6
Validation study:	5.5
Review:	4.1
Workshop:	3.1
Dissertation:	4.4
Randomized controlled trial:	3.1
Web:	3.1
Systematic review:	2.2
Descriptive study:	2.2
Article:	2.2

Blog post:	2.2
Mixed methods study:	1.8
Pilot study:	1.7
Book:	1.4
Erasmus+ project:	1.4
Cross-sectional study:	1.4
Qualitative study:	1.1
Research Project:	1.1
App:	0.8
Newsletter:	0.8
Effectiveness study:	0.8
Retrospective study:	0.6
Protocol:	0.6
Repository:	0.6
Ebook:	0.3
Website database	0.3
Book chapter:	0.3
Digital newsletter:	0.3
Other	0.3

Table 9. Type of practice/policy data included in the GALHDataset2 (%)

13 Horizon 2020 projects and 1 Erasmus+ were included in the GALH. These projects impacted in 28 countries and appear in 122 records of the practice/policy dataset (Table 10)

European project	Number
Horizon 2020	13
Erasmus+	1
Countries	28
Records in dataset	122

Table 10. Quantity of Horizon 2020 and Erasmus+ projects included in the GALH.

Spain is the country with more practices, policy and initiatives included in the practice/policy dataset of the GALH (table 11).

Country	%
Spain	28.5
Australia	5.6
Germany	5.4
Netherlands	4.9
USA	4.6
UK	4.1
Italy	4.1
Finland	3.9
Portugal	3.9
France	2.9
Denmark	2.4
Belgium	2.2
Ireland	2.2
Austria	2.2
Sweden	2.0
Greece	1.7
Romania	1.2
Norway	1.2
Switzerland	1.2

Table 11. GALH practice, interventions and initiatives data per country: Europe and Beyond (%)

Most of the practices refer to HL (52,1%) as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Type of HL of the practice/policy, initiatives and projects included in the GALH.

3.2 FAQ

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) are useful on a website for several reasons:

- Quick access to relevant information: FAQs allow visitors to find quick answers to common questions without having to extensively search the website. This improves the user experience and saves time.
- Time and resource-saving: By providing answers to frequently asked questions in advance, the need for users to directly contact the support or customer service team for answers is reduced, saving time and resources for both the user and the team behind the website.
- Clarity and understanding: FAQs can help clarify doubts and provide more detailed explanations about products, services, or concepts that might be confusing to visitors. This enhances understanding and perception of the brand or website.
- Building trust: A website that includes a well-organized and comprehensive FAQ section shows that the site cares about its users and is willing to provide relevant and helpful information. This can help build trust and credibility with visitors.

- **Visibility:** FAQs may contain relevant keywords that users might search for in search engines. This can improve the website's ranking in search results and increase online visibility.
- **Fewer repetitive inquiries:** By addressing common questions through FAQs, the number of repetitive inquiries received by the support or customer service team will be reduced, allowing them to focus on more complex or specific issues.
- **Highlighting features and benefits:** FAQs can be used to highlight unique features or key benefits of products or services, helping to capture users' attention and encourage conversion or adoption.

In summary, a well-designed and up-to-date FAQ page can enhance the user experience, save time and resources, and increase trust and credibility for a website or online business.

A link to the Health Literacy Tool Shed (bu.edu) is suggested in the FAQ (Boston University, 2023) so that users can find detailed information on HL scales.

The frequently asked questions, which can be found on the IDEAHL website, can be found in Annex 5.

3.3 GET IN TOUCH

Maintaining an updated interactive map of health literacy data can provide several advantages for both healthcare professionals and the general public. Some of the prominent benefits include:

- **Clear and accessible visualization:** An interactive map offers a visually appealing and easy-to-understand way to present health literacy data. People can quickly comprehend the information through charts, colors, and geographical markers.
- **Identification of critical areas:** The map can help identify regions with low levels of health literacy, enabling professionals and policymakers to focus resources and programs where they are most needed.
- **Detection of trends and patterns:** By analyzing geographic data over time, emerging trends and patterns in health literacy can be detected. This facilitates the planning of health promotion interventions and strategies.

- Personalization of messages and resources: With an interactive map, it is possible to tailor health messages and resources to the specific needs of each region or community, considering their literacy levels and understanding.
- Facilitates informed decision-making: Healthcare professionals and policymakers can make more informed decisions by relying on accurate and updated data on the health literacy of a particular population.
- Promotion of transparency: An interactive map displaying reliable and updated data promotes transparency in the healthcare field, allowing people to access relevant information openly.
- Tracking progress: By regularly updating the interactive map, progress in improving health literacy over time can be tracked. This helps assess the effectiveness of interventions and make adjustments if necessary.
- Public awareness and education: Presenting data interactively fosters public awareness of the importance of health literacy and its impact on individual and community health.
- Collaboration and information sharing: An interactive map can be a collaborative tool that involves different healthcare organizations and communities in sharing data and working together towards joint improvement efforts.

In conclusion, maintaining an updated interactive map of health literacy data can have a significant impact on health promotion, effective intervention planning, and overall well-being of the population.

The users of the Atlas can report new studies, interventions and initiatives via this form.:
https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1tI_lqWeWS1-3Q8ef507wX3fDFyVEJYDdw-15JoUSPns/viewform?pli=1&ts=646e0cb4&pli=1&edit_requested=true

3.4 GLOSSARY AND DATA DICTIONARY

The sections are:

* The Glossary: you can find it at the beginning of the deliverable.

* The Data: you can find it in annex 1.

4. HOW TO USE THE GALH IN 10 SIMPLE STEPS

The GALH can be accessed via the website of the IDEAHL project and/or the RMIT website at www.rmit.eu/GALH.

- 1) **Access the website www.rmit.eu/GALH** and click ACCESS
- 2) **Read the description and frequently asked questions**
- 3) **Click access the GALH** of the IDEAHL project. When accessing the GALH the interactive map is first seen as shown in figure 3. The highlight variables of the interactive map are:
 - Literacy type: health literacy, digital health literacy or both. If “both” is selected the map will show the total of included studies.
 - Population: children and adolescents, general adult population, healthcare workforce and patients
 - Scale: the name of the scale used to measure the level of (d)HL
 - Range: the maximum value possible in the specific scale to measure the level of (d)HL.
 - Country count: The number of countries that were measured with the scale and target population
 - Article count: The number of articles that featured each scale.

Figure 4. First page of the GALH via the website

- 4) In the interactive map the levels of (d)HL are shown in choropleths (figure 4). A choropleth map is a type of thematic map utilized to depict statistical data through color mapping symbology technique. It presents enumeration units, which are divided geographical areas or regions, colored, shaded, or patterned in accordance with a specific data variable. It is possible to select the data to be seen whether it is related to health literacy, digital health literacy or both. After this selection, the user can choose the target population and scale and the choropleths the minimum and maximum value range.
- 5) With the country count (C) and article count (A) users can **find out the number of countries** that were measured with the scale and target population and the number of articles that featured each scale.
- 6) By **clicking in a country** (figure 5) users can see the level of (d)HL reported for a particular scale in a study and also benchmark with additional scales used in the country for the same target population.

Figure 5. Country level monitoring data in interactive map

- 7) By clicking in “view map data” (figure 6) users can access to the entire dataset that is visualized in the interactive map. Users can also filter the information for all the countries or a particular country of their interest.

Global Atlas of Literacies for Health

[Interactive map](#) [Measurements data](#) [Practice/policy data](#)

Health literacy Digital health literacy Both

Population	Scale	Range	C	A
children and adolescents	HLSAC	/40	9	6
general adult population	HLS-EU-Child-Q15	/100	2	2
health workforce	DHLI	/100	1	1
patients	eHEALS	/5	1	1
	EHML	mean score	1	1
	HLS5item/EDUFI	/100	1	1
	HLSAC	mean score	1	1
	HLSAC	/100	1	1
	NVS Pteen	/100	1	1
	SCCHL	/100	1	1

filter for ⓘ

HLSAC ⓘ children and adolescents

[view map data](#)

Figure 6. View map data and filter by country in the interactive map.

8) When users click “view map data” in the map or “measurement data” in the right corner of map they will see the raw data, a descriptive note and a link to read the study where the data came from. (figure 7).

In this view, users can see:

- Country: The country
- Population: the target population
- Scale: the name of the measure
- Scale value: the value of the measure for that particular target population of that particular country
- Scale range: the maximum possible value of the scale (or adaptation of the scale)
- Coverage: limited or good country coverage categorized through the sample size and sampling method of the study (random sampling vs. non probabilistic methods).
- A descriptive note that describes the title of the article, the authors' last names, the target population of the study, the sample size, the name of the measure, the reported levels of (d)HL, the validation of the tool (if there is mention in the article about the validation process of the used scale or if the scale is validated).

Global Atlas of Literacies for Health

Interactive map | **Measurements data** | Practice/policy data

Country | Scale /40 | Population

Country	Population	Scale	Scale value	Scale range	Coverage
Belgium	children and adolescents	HLSAC	29.33	/40	limited
Denmark	children and adolescents	HLSAC	29.83	/40	limited
Finland	children and adolescents	HLSAC	33.3	/40	limited
Finland	children and adolescents	HLSAC	33.11	/40	limited
Germany	children and adolescents	HLSAC	31.28	/40	limited
Italy	children and adolescents	HLSAC	29.08	/40	limited
Netherlands	children and adolescents	HLSAC	32.55	/40	good
Poland	children and adolescents	HLSAC	20.69	/40	limited
Poland	children and adolescents	HLSAC	30.57	/40	limited
Slovakia	children and adolescents	HLSAC	31.33	/40	limited
Sweden	children and adolescents	HLSAC	32.4	/40	limited

Title
The cross-national measurement invariance of the health literacy for school-aged children (Hlsac) instrument

Authors
Paakkari O, Torppa M, Boberova Z, Valimaa R, Maier G, Mazur J, Kannas L, Paakkari L

Target population
13 years and 15 years old pupils from Belgium, Finland, Poland and Slovakia (n= 1468).

Sample size
From Belgium: 15 years old pupils n=184 (No 13 years old pupils at all)

Measure(s)
HLSAC

HL and dHL levels
Mean HL in Belgium for pupils aged 15 was 29.33%

For 15 years old pupils Poland and Slovakia showed no difference from Belgium. Compared to Finland, Belgium pupils had lower HL values.

Validation
The tool was validated in this study. The instrument exhibited high internal consistency and showed adequate fit with the data. It was concluded that HL mean values assessed via the HLSAC instrument can be compared across countries. The instrument has utility for large-scale international HL studies on adolescents.

Figure 7. Measurement data.

9) When clicking in the **practice/policy data** users will see a repository of practices, policy, interventions, initiatives and (d) HL. As explained before this data is not possible to visualize in choropleth as the variables included in the dataset are mainly open text and string. Users can access these resources by clicking in the links provided and can also read a descriptive note with a brief description of the resource (including when possible target population, validation process, measure or tool used).

Global Atlas of Literacies for Health

Interactive map Measurements data Practice/policy data

Figure 8. Practice/Police Data

10) When clicking the Practice/Policy data users can filter the information by country (figure9).

Figure 9. Country specific practice/policy data

The GALH of the IDEAHL project repository of research articles includes a note section. The note comes from deliverable 1.1 of the IDEAHL project and were extracted from the analysis of task 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 of WP1. End-users can access the complete references of the article and also a brief summary of the extracted data. This will help to contextualize and understand the type of research, country coverage, sample size and target population where the (d)HL levels visualized in the Atlas come from.

The "Note" section is intended to aid in the understanding of complex scientific information for the general public. In the note users can find the title of the study, practice, initiative or policy, the authors, a description of the target population that participated in the measurement and/or practice, the sample size, the tool or measure that was used, the HL and dHL levels that were reported in the studies and the validation of the scale. The validation refers to the overall validity of the results reported in the studies. Moreover, users can find a link to the full texts of the studies and initiatives, practice and policies included in the GALH, to deepen their analysis and interpretation of dHL and HL.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The GALH is a resource addressed to citizens, health organisations, government and policy makers exploring the health literacy of the general population, children and young people, patients, and the health workforce. Examples of practice to improve literacy will assist these stakeholders in identifying how other countries have planned and actioned literacy improvement and the change in literacy as a result.

Understanding trends in different literacy scales for a region can inform scholarly teaching needs, research and policy making, health care patient needs and citizens. Different literacy needs can be targeted in curriculum and research development, health programs, policy and care depending on the discipline and regional needs. In the area of health, it is important to not only develop the health and digital literacy rates knowledge in general but to clearly understand the literacy rates of the different target populations that will eventually receive treatment and care and be subject of policies and interventions. Yet, there are over one hundred different literacy tools available, as shown in the Health Literacy Tool Shed LH of the IDEAHL project, therefore, is developed as tool that not only summarises the various literacy scales but presents the empirical evidence for how they have been used or evaluated in different geographical regions practice, interventions and initiatives so that the users can fully understand it and make use of it.

LIMITATIONS: the datasets developed to include data in the GALH come from different collaborative scientific and grey literature reviews (11). The limitations of these reviews also apply to the GALH, as it is a visualization and systematization of those results to be easily and comprehensibly accessible by different stakeholders. As a result of the co-creation process with experts, it was stated that there is a risk of missing data that is why a process for collecting new data via an online form was established and scheduled updates are planned within the duration of the project.

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7. TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1. Data extraction related to included studies in literatures reviews of IDEAHL WP1

Table 2. Records and variables of GALH datasets

Table 3. GALH Dataset1: Monitoring/Scales Levels DATA

Table 4. GALH dataset2 repository of Practice/Police DATA

Table 5. Inclusion in interactive map

Table 6. Workshops with dHL and Digital Health Experts.

Table 7. GALH of the IDEAHL project monitoring scale levels data per country. Europe and Beyond (record count)

Table 8. GALH of the IDEAHL project monitoring scale levels data per country and target population. Europe and Beyond (record count)

Table 9. Type of practice/policy data included in the GALH Dataset2 (%)

Table 10. Quantity of Horizon 2020 and Erasmus+ projects included in the GALH.

Table 11. GALH practice, interventions and initiatives data per country: Europe and Beyond (%)

Table 12– GALH Monitoring dataset

Table 13 – GALH Best Practice, Interventions and Initiatives dataset

Figure 1. Three phases of the development of GALH of the IDEAHL project

Figure 2. Flyers of invitation to the workshops and testing of the GALH of the IDEAHL project

Figure 3. Type of HL of the practice/policy, initiatives and projects included in the GALH.

Figure 4. First page of the GALH via the website

Figure 5. Country level monitoring data in interactive map

Figure 6. View map data and filter by country in the interactive map.

Figure 7. Measurement data.

Figure 8. Practice/Police Data

Figure 9. Country specific practice/policy data

8. ANNEXES

- **ANNEX I. DATA DICTIONARY**
- **ANNEX II. MONITORING DATASET**
- **ANNEX III. REFERENCE REPOSITORY DATASET**
- **ANNEX IV. LANDING PAGE IDEAHL GALH WEBPAGE**
- **ANNEX V. FAQs in GALH WEBSITE**

ANNEX I. DATA DICTIONARY

The following table shows the definitions, which have been assigned to the data categories that have been used to organise the information obtained from the IDEAHL WP1 literature search.

Data available for monitoring, evaluation and (d)HL	
Country	The name of the country in the EU or Beyond where the monitoring or evaluation of levels of (d) HL study was conducted
Population	The population that the monitoring of (d) HL studies reach
First Author	The first author listed in the publication from which the data was extracted
Scale	Monitoring and evaluation tools, methods, and frameworks in (d)HL that are validated and published in peer-reviewed journals; they measure/quantify individuals' (d)HL (9) and organisations' HL and (d)HL environments covering different target populations and services (See list of SCALES e.g., the HLS-EU questionnaire, the eHL Assessment toolkit (eHLA) and the eHL Questionnaire (eHLQ), HLQ, BRIEF, etc). A health literacy scale is a standardized questionnaire or survey designed to capture various aspects of health literacy, such as the ability to understand and use health information, navigate healthcare systems, and make informed decisions about health. These scales typically consist of a series of questions or statements that respondents rate or respond to, providing quantitative data on their health literacy abilities. Health literacy scales are valuable in research, evaluation, and intervention efforts, helping to identify gaps, track progress, and tailor interventions to improve health literacy and promote better health outcomes. The GALH compiles different types of scales that measure (d)HL, to see a complete description of the scale and how it is implemented you could either see the reference and read the study where it was applied or visit the Health Literacy Tool Shed (bu.edu) where you can find detailed information on HL scales.
Coverage	The coverage of the findings and conclusions on (d)HL and HL levels of the monitoring studies based on the sample size, design and recruitment method. (Limited country coverage or good country coverage).
Note	The note section provides a condensed overview of information derived from analyzing monitoring levels of (d)HL. It is presented in a concise format using to emphasize key points. However, it is recommended to refer to the full text for a comprehensive understanding of the studies' scope. Moreover, it is advisable to read Buhl Povlsen M, Brun Thorup C, Schack Thoft D, Korsbakke Emtekær Hæsum L, Valkama K, Uitto M, et al. D1.1. Report on (d)HL WP1 . IDEAHL; https://ideahl.eu/ . This ensures a more complete grasp of the subject matter and enables a deeper comprehension of the topic at hand.

	The notes provided are derived from four distinct literature review analyses and are presented in various formats. Some notes include details such as the design of the intervention, its objectives, the intended audience, barriers and facilitators, and key factors. Additionally, certain notes also offer insights into the practical implications and monitoring considerations, while others provide a concise narrative description of the topic.
Data available for best practice, policy, interventions and initiatives	
Country	The name of the country in the EU or Beyond where the intervention, initiative, practice or policy is or has been conducted.
Title	The name of the intervention, initiative, practice or policy.
Lead Organisation	The name of the main organisation or coordinating entity that lead or developed the intervention, initiative, practice or policy in (d) HL
First Author	The first author listed in the publication from which the data was extracted
Other authors	Other authors listed in the publication from which the data was extracted
Year (start)	The start date of the intervention, initiative, practice or policy in (d)HL
Year (last)	The end date of the intervention, initiative, practice or policy in (d)HL
Status	The status of the intervention, initiative, practice or policy in (d) HL: ongoing, active, completed, published.
HL, dHL, (d)HL, other	The literacy addressed by the intervention, initiative, practice, or policy: Health Literacy, digital health literacy, both or other literacies.
International/National/Regional/local	The geographical scope of the intervention, initiative, practice or policy in (d)HL
Public/Private	A public intervention is one that is initiated, funded, or overseen by a government or public sector entity. It is typically aimed at addressing public needs or societal issues and is funded through public resources.: A private intervention is initiated, funded, or operated by private entities, such as industry, non-profit organisations, or individual practitioners
Type	report, book, PhD dissertation, health plan, blog, web, project, validation study, effectiveness study, randomized controlled study, mixed-methods study, cross-sectional study, other
Age group	The age group that the intervention, initiative, practice or policy target (Adults, Children, adolescents, Seniors, general)
Target Group	The group level that the intervention, initiative, practice or policy reach (citizens, students, health workforce, patients, other)
Level	The level that the intervention, initiative, practice or policy reach (individual, family, community, group, society, organisational)
Sector	The sector that the intervention, initiative, practice or policy relate to (Academia, Education, Industry, Public Health, Health, Promotion, Nutrition, other)

Tool, measure or scale	The tool, scale or measure mentioned in the intervention, initiative, practice or policy to conduct measurements of (d)HL
Champion	<i>Champions</i> = Professionals, services, organisations, municipalities, regions, etc. that published a peer reviewed article in a scientific journal providing evidence of success with initiatives (best practices) in relation to (d)HL ie: the initiatives showed improvement of levels of HL with pre test and post test measurement
Reference	The reference provides essential information about the source from which the data has been extracted, allowing readers to locate and access the referenced material.
Note	The note section provides a condensed overview of information derived from analyzing best practices, interventions, policies, and initiatives. It is presented in a concise format using bullet points to emphasize key points. However, it is recommended to refer to the full text, websites, or reports for a comprehensive understanding of the interventions' scope. Moreover, it is advisable to read Buhl Povlsen M, Brun Thorup C, Schack Thoft D, Korsbakke Emtækær Hæsum L, Valkama K, Uitto M, et al. D1.1. Report on (d)HL WP1 . IDEAHL; https://ideahl.eu/ . This ensures a more complete grasp of the subject matter and enables a deeper comprehension of the topic at hand. The notes provided are derived from four distinct literature review analyses and are presented in various formats. Some notes include details such as the design of the intervention, its objectives, the intended audience, barriers and facilitators, and key factors. Additionally, certain notes also offer insights into the practical implications and monitoring considerations, while others provide a concise narrative description of the topic.

ANNEX II. MONITORING DATASET

Table 12– GALH Monitoring dataset

Record count	First author	Country
1	Putz	Austria
2	Gerich	Austria
3	Maitz	Austria
4	Paakkari	Belgium
5	Hermans	Belgium
6	Storms	Belgium
7	Ritchie	Belgium
8	Pelikan	Bulgaria
9	Brangan	Croatia
10	Efthymiou	Cyprus
11	Rolová	Czechia
12	Chraskova	Czechia
13	Aaby	Denmark
14	Kyser	Denmark
15	Karnoe	Denmark
16	Schwennesen	Denmark
17	Rosen	Denmark
18	Holt	Denmark
19	Lindskrog	Denmark
20	Aaby	Denmark
21	Holt	Denmark
22	Fris	Denmark
23	Svendsen	Denmark
24	Bonde	Denmark
25	Bak	Denmark
26	Kayser	Denmark
27	Eronen	Finland
28	Eronen	Finland
29	Summanen	Finland
30	Kinnunen	Finland
31	Paakkari	Finland

32	Perrin	France
33	Ousseine	France
34	Debussche	France
35	Rouquette	France
36	Ousseine	France
37	Ritchie	France
38	Berens	Germany
39	<u>Heiman</u>	Germany
40	Oedekoven	Germany
41	Atmann	Germany
42	Köhler	Germany
43	Bollweg	Germany
44	Nakata	Germany
45	Knitza	Germany
46	Loer	Germany
47	Dadaczynski	Germany
48	Steinke	Germany
49	Pfob	Germany
50	Spinler	Germany
51	Stock	Germany
52	De Santis	Germany
53	Rohwer	Germany
54	Marsall	Germany
55	Gernert	Germany
56	Dadaczynski	Germany
57	Reichel	Germany
58	Samkange-Zeeb	Germany
59	Pelikan	Germany
60	Kinnunen	Germany
61	Taoufik	Greece
62	Kritsotakis	Greece
63	Trantali	Greece
64	Pelikan	Greece
65	Efthymiou	Greece
66	Erdei	Hungary
67	Zrubka	Hungary
68	Náfrádi	Hungary

69	Zrubka	Hungary
70	Bánfai-Csonka	Hungary
71	Bíró	Hungary
72	Sántha	Hungary
73	Mathew	Ireland
74	Clarke	Ireland
75	Jackson	Ireland
76	Mackey	Ireland
77	Delemere	Ireland
78	Pelikan	Ireland
79	Gibney	Ireland
80	Palumbo	Italy
81	Lorini	Italy
82	Dellapelle	Italy
83	Biasio	Italy
84	Del Giudice	Italy
85	Lorini	Italy
86	Bonnaccorsi	Italy
87	Schiavone	Italy
88	Lorini	Italy
89	Velasco	Italy
90	Magon	Italy
91	Bevilacqua	Italy
92	Lastrucci	Italy
93	Lorini	Italy
94	Ritchie	Italy
95	Jansen	Netherlands
96	Woudstra	Netherlands
97	Hahnraths	Netherlands
98	Pelikan	Netherlands
99	Kinnunen	Netherlands
100	Reichel	Netherlands
101	Kosicka	Poland
102	Mazur	Poland
103	Duplaga	Poland
104	Burzynska	Poland
105	Mirczak	Poland
106	Pelikan	Poland

107	Paakkari	Poland
108	Santos	Portugal
109	Dias	Portugal
110	Espíritu-Santo	Portugal
111	Pedro	Portugal
112	Pires	Portugal
113	Ferreira	Portugal
114	Arriaga	Portugal
115	Samkange-Zeed	Portugal
116	Medina	Portugal
117	Costa	Portugal
118	Batista de Araujo	Portugal
119	Do Ó	Portugal
120	Barros	Portugal
121	Sfeactu	Romania
122	Coman	Romania
123	Sántha	Romania
124	Timková	Slovakia
125	Paakkari	Slovakia
126	Sántha	Slovakia
127	Castro Sánchez	Spain
128	Cabellos Garcia	Spain
129	Correa Rodriguez	Spain
130	Castelvi	Spain
131	Nolasco	Spain
132	Santesmases-Masana	Spain
133	Garcia-Codina	Spain
134	Bas Sarmiento	Spain
135	Pelikan	Spain
136	Ritchie	Spain
137	Viktorsson	Sweden
138	Wångdahl	Sweden
139	Jacobsson	Sweden
140	Wångdahl	Sweden
141	Bergman	Sweden
142	Jaensson	Sweden
143	Mekhail	Sweden
144	Brown	England

145	Gonzalez	USA
146	Nouri	USA
147	Carrol	USA
148	Warring	USA
149	Toibin	Ireland
150	Maitz	Austria
151	De Buhr	Germany
152	Kaper	Netherlands
153	Muscat	Australia
154	Redfern	Australia
155	Armstrong-Heimsoth	USA
156	Pelikan	Austria
157	Pelikan	Belgium
158	Pelikan	Bulgaria
159	Pelikan	Czechia
160	Pelikan	Denmark
161	Pelikan	Germany
162	Pelikan	France
163	Pelikan	Hungary
164	Pelikan	Ireland
165	Pelikan	Italy
166	Pelikan	Norway
167	Pelikan	Portugal
168	Pelikan	Slovenia
169	Pelikan	Slovakia
170	HLS19 M-POHL	Austria
171	HLS19 M-POHL	Belgium
172	HLS19 M-POHL	Czechia
173	HLS19 M-POHL	Germany
174	HLS19 M-POHL	Denmark
175	HLS19 M-POHL	France
176	HLS19 M-POHL	Hungary
177	HLS19 M-POHL	Ireland
178	HLS19 M-POHL	Norway
179	HLS19 M-POHL	Portugal
180	HLS19 M-POHL	Slovakia
181	HLS19 M-POHL	Austria
182	HLS19 M-POHL	Belgium

183	HLS19 M-POHL	Bulgaria
184	HLS19 M-POHL	Czechia
185	HLS19 M-POHL	Germany
186	HLS19 M-POHL	Hungary
187	HLS19 M-POHL	Ireland
188	HLS19 M-POHL	Italy
189	HLS19 M-POHL	Norway
190	HLS19 M-POHL	Portugal
191	HLS19 M-POHL	Slovakia
192	Schaeffer	Germany
193	Koster	Netherlands

Table 13 – GALH Best Practice, Interventions and Initiatives dataset

Record count	Lead Organisation	First author	Country
1	Dansk Selskab for Folkesundhed (DSFF)	Aaby	Denmark
2	Danish Health and Medicines Authority	Aaby	Denmark
3	Finnish National Agency for Education		Finland
	Finnish National Agency for Education		Finland
4	Finnish Government		Finland
5	Tampere University of Applied Sciences		Finland
6	University of Turku		Finland
7	University of Jyväskylä	Paakkari	Poland
4	University of Jyväskylä	Paakkari	Slovakia
5	University of Jyväskylä	Paakkari	Belgium
6	University of Jyväskylä	Paakkari	Finland
	University of Oulu	Hirvonen	Finland
8	Jamk University of Applied Sciences	Nurmeksela	Finland
9	Bundesministerium für Gesundheit		Germany
10	Bundesministerium für Gesundheit		Germany
11	Bundesministerium für Gesundheit		Germany
12	Universität Bielefeld		Germany
13	Ministero della Salute		Italy
14	Ministero delle Imprese e del Made in Italy		Italy
15	Istituto Superiore di Sanità	Bravo	Italy
16	Ministério da Saúde. Direção-Geral da Saúde	de Arriaga	Portugal
17	Ministério da Saúde. Direção-Geral da Saúde	Almeida	Portugal
18	Fundação Francisco Manuel dos Santos	Mendes Ribeiro	Portugal
19	Centro de Edições do ISPA	Lopes	Portugal
20	Instituto da Saúde Pública	Oliveira	Portugal
21	Instituto Politécnico do Porto	Silva	Portugal
22	Ministério da Saúde		Portugal
23	Escola Nacional de Saúde Pública	Pedro	Portugal
24	Instituto Superior de Psicologia Aplicada	Antunes	Portugal
25	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Pisano González	Spain
26	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Spain
27	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Spain

28	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Spain
29	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Spain
30	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Spain
31	Ministerio de Sanidad España	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Spain
32	Ministerio de Salud Cataluña	González Mestre	Spain
33	Ministerio de Salud Islas Canarias		Spain
34	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Esparza	Spain
35	Ministerio de Salud Asturias	Mosquera	Spain
36	Ministerio de Salud Asturias		Spain
37	Fundación Internet, Salud y Sociedad		Spain
38	Fundación Gaspar Casal		Spain
39	Asociación Salud Digital -ASD-	Moya	Spain
40	Associació Centre d'Higiene Mental Les Cort		Spain
41	Associació Centre d'Higiene Mental Les Cort		Spain
42	Servicio Canario de Salud (FIISC)		Spain
43	SaludConectada		Spain
44	Asociación de Profesionales en Prevención y Postvención del Suicidio		Spain
45	Asociación para la ayuda a personas afectadas por el VIH/sida - OMSIDA -		Spain
46	Fundación IMAS		Spain
47	Salud Digital-Fundación Carlos Slim		Mexico
48	Col·legi de Farmacèutics de Barcelona (COFB)		Spain
49	Salud Digital-Fundación Carlos Slim		Spain
50	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)		Spain
51	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)	Hernández	Spain
52	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)	Hernández	Spain
53	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)	PSINET Psychology	Spain
54	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)	Carrión	Spain
55	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)	Hernandez	Spain
56	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)		Spain
57	Universitat de Girona	Juvinyà	Spain
58	Universitat de Girona		Spain
59	Universitat de Girona		Spain
60	Red Interuniversitaria euroamericana de investigación sobre competencias mediáticas para la ciudadanía (Red Alfamed)		Spain

61	Fundación Universitaria San Antonio (UCAM)		Spain
62	Escuela Andaluza de Salud Pública	Morgan	Spain
63	Generalitat de Catalunya		Spain
64	Ministerio de Salud Islas Canarias		Spain
65	Junta de Andalucía. Consejería de Salud y Consumo		Spain
66	Junta de Andalucía. Consejería de Salud y Consumo	March	Spain
67	Escuela Andaluza de Salud Pública		Spain
68	Agencia de Calidad y Evaluación Sanitarias de Catalunya		Spain
69	Hospital Germans Trias		Spain
70	L'Insitut Català de la Salut a Girona		Spain
71	Generalitat de Catalunya		Spain
72	Diputació Barcelona		Spain
73	Red de Investigación en Servicios de Salud en Enfermedades Crónicas (REDISSEC)		Spain
74	Red Pública de Bibliotecas		Spain
75	Federación Española de Municipios y Provincias		Spain
76	Ministerio de Salud Asturias		Spain
77	Servicio de Salud de las Islas Baleares	Sastre Perea	Spain
78	Generalitat Valenciana		Spain
79	Departamento de Salud Gobierno Vasco		Spain
80	Departament de Salut. Generalitat de Catalunya.		Spain
81	Escuela Madrileña de Salud		Spain
82	Consellería de Sanidade Servizo Galego de Saúde		Spain
83	Institut Català de la Salut		Spain
84	Diputació de Girona		Spain
85	Institut Català de Salut		Spain
86	Servei Català de Salut		Spain
87	Hospital Clínico Universitario Virgen de la Arrixaca Murcia		Spain
88	Sociedad Española de Documentación e Información Científica (SEDIC)		Spain
89	Red.es		Spain
90	Generalitat de Catalunya		Spain
91	Biblioteca Marquesa de Pelayo, Escuela Cántabra de Salud		Spain
92	TICSalut Social		Spain
93	TICSalut Social		Spain
94	TICSalut Social		Spain
95	Asociación Salud Digital		Spain
96	Fundación Gaspar Casal		Spain
97	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC)		Spain

98	Universidad Pompeu Fabra	Estopà	Spain
99	La Xarxa Catalana d'Hospitals i Centres Promotors de la Salut (HPH Catalunya)	Suñer Soler	Spain
100	La Xarxa Catalana d'Hospitals i Centres Promotors de la Salut (HPH Catalunya)		Spain
101	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, Universitat de Cádiz-Facultad de Enfermería, Servicio de Evaluación del Servicio Canario de Salud, Universitat de Girona- Càtedra de Promoció de la Salut Facultat d'Infermeria, Universidad de Murcia, Escola Galega de Saúde para Cidadáns, Servizio Galego de Saúde, Escuela de Salud de Aragón		Spain
102	Escuela Andaluza de Salud Pública		Spain
103	Cibersalud: salud mental online		Spain
104	Red de investigación en actividades preventivas y promoción de la salud		Spain
105	Generalitat Valenciana		Spain
106	Generalitat Valenciana		Spain
107	Revista Salud Digital		Spain
108	Asepeyo Salud (hospitales)		Spain
109	Cura e Salud		Spain
110	Gobierno de España		Spain
111	Universidad Santiago de Compostela		Spain
112	Sociedad Española de Informática de la Salud	Sampedro	Spain
113	Servicio de Interpretación de Lengua de Signos de Extremadura		Spain
114	Secretaría General de Salud Digital		Spain
115	Centro de Salud Mental de Adultos Martí i Julià, Parc de Salut Mar, Barcelona, España	López-Santin	Spain
116	Federación Española de Empresas de Tecnología Sanitaria		Spain
117	Junta de Extremadura		Spain
118	Agencia de Calidad Sanitaria de Andalucía (ACSA)		Spain
119	Gobierno de España		Spain
120	Asociación Salud Digital	Jaumandreu	Spain
121	EAVI Media Literacy for Citizenship		Belgium
122	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		UK
123	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Switzerland
124	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Austria
125	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Czechia
126	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Germany
127	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Poland
128	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Italy
129	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Belgium
130	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Netherlands

131	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Saudi Arabia
132	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Norway
133	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Ireland
134	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		France
135	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Israel
136	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Turkey
137	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Croatia
138	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht, coord.		Spain
139	Universiteit Maastricht, coord.		Netherlands
140	Universiteit Maastricht, coord.		USA
141	Universiteit Maastricht, coord.		Netherlands
142	Universiteit Maastricht, coord.		Germany
143	Universiteit Maastricht, coord.		Spain
144	Universiteit Maastricht, coord.		UK
145	Universitat Zurich, coord.		Switzerland
146	Universitat Zurich, coord.		USA
147	Fundación para el Fomento de la Investigación Sanitaria y Biomédica de la Comunitat Valenciana, coord.		Spain
148	Fundación para el Fomento de la Investigación Sanitaria y Biomédica de la Comunitat Valenciana, coord.		Italy
149	Fundación para el Fomento de la Investigación Sanitaria y Biomédica de la Comunitat Valenciana, coord.		UK
150	Fundación para el Fomento de la Investigación Sanitaria y Biomédica de la Comunitat Valenciana, coord.		France
151	Universitetssykehuset Nord-Norge HF, coord.		Norway
152	Universitetssykehuset Nord-Norge HF, coord.		Romania
153	Universitetssykehuset Nord-Norge HF, coord.		Spain
154	Universitetssykehuset Nord-Norge HF, coord.		Ireland
155	Universitetssykehuset Nord-Norge HF, coord.		Italy
156	Universitetssykehuset Nord-Norge HF, coord.		Bulgaria
157	Universitetssykehuset Nord-Norge HF, coord.		Finland
158	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Greece
159	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Bulgaria
160	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Albania
161	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Australia
162	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		USA
163	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Italy
164	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Belgium
165	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Spain
166	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		Netherlands

167	Charokopeio Paneptimimi, coord.		France
168	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Greece
169	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Spain
170	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Romania
171	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Luxembourg
172	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Switzerland
173	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Serbia
174	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Germany
175	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		UK
176	Gioumpitek Meleti Schediasmos Ylopoiisi Kai Polisi Ergon Pliroforikis Etaireia Periorismenis Efthynis, coord.		Sweden
177	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		Germany
178	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		Hungary
179	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		UK
180	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		France
181	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		Sweden
182	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		Latvia
183	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		Turkey
184	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		Norway
185	Aarhus Universitet, coord.		Serbia
186	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		Greece
187	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		UK
188	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		Italy
189	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		Romania
190	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		Norway
191	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		Luxembourg
192	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		Spain
193	Erevnitiko Panepistimiako Institouto Systimatou Epikoinonion Kai Ypologisto, coord.		Cyprus
194	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, coord.		Spain

195	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, coord.		Portugal
196	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, coord.		Serbia
197	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, coord.		Ireland
198	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, coord.		Belgium
199	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse, coord.		Austria
200	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse, coord.		Netherlands
201	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse, coord.		Netherlands
202	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse, coord.		Germany
203	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse, coord.		Greece
204	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse, coord.		Spain
205	Internationales Institut für Angewandte Systemanalyse, coord.		Austria
206	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Austria
207	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Italy
208	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Sweden
209	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Finland
210	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Luxembourg
211	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Greece
212	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Netherlands
213	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Germany
214	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Cyprus
215	FH Joanneum Gesellschaft MBH, coord.		Belgium
216	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		Greece
217	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		Spain
218	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		Bulgaria
219	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		Belgium
220	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		Italy
221	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		Romania
222	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		UK
223	University of Piraeus Research Center, coord.		Sweden
224	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Spain
225	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Germany
226	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Italy
227	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Netherlands
228	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Slovenia

229	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Germany
230	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Italy
231	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Austria
232	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		UK
233	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		France
234	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Czechia
235	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Belgium
236	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Finland
237	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		Switzerland
238	Fundación Instituto de Estudios de Ciencias de la Salud de Castilla y León, coord.		USA
239	FH JOANNEUM University of Applied Sciences, coord.		Spain
240	FH JOANNEUM University of Applied Sciences, coord.		Germany
241	FH JOANNEUM University of Applied Sciences, coord.		Netherlands
242	FH JOANNEUM University of Applied Sciences, coord.		Finland
243	FH JOANNEUM University of Applied Sciences, coord.		Austria
244		Pinderup	Denmark
245		Jensen	Denmark
246		Zenas	Denmark
247		Jensen	Denmark
248		Pinderup	Denmark
249		Zenas	Denmark
250		Rouquette	France
251		Perrin	France
252		Henrard	France
253		Domanska	Germany
254		Bollweg	Germany
255		Weber	Germany
256		Lorini	Italy
257		Martins	Portugal
258		Paiva	Portugal
259		Burns	Australia
260		Forbes	UK

261		Uribe Guajardo	Australia
262		Uribe Guajardo	Australia
263		Gurung	USA
264		Wei Liu	USA
265		Hart	Australia
266		van der Giessen	Netherlands
267		Kurki	Finland
268		Lee	USA
269		Lindow	USA
270		Loureiro	Portugal
271		Michalowski	USA
272		O'Connell	Ireland
273		Sinclair	USA
274		Morgan	Australia
275		Slewa-Younan	Australia
276		Thorsteinsson	Australia
277		Wei	Canada
278		Wynters	Australia
279		Muller	UK
280		Seidling	Germany
281		Hart	Australia
282		Queroue	France
283		Stanifer	USA
284		Patafio	Australia
285		Carroll	USA
286		Warring	USA
287		Toibin	Ireland
288		Maitz	Austria
289		De Buhr	Germany
290		Kaper	Netherlands
291		Muscat	Australia
292		Brown	UK
293		Gonzalez	USA
294		Nouri	USA
295		Konopik	Germany
296		Koster	Netherlands
297		Abdullah	Netherlands
298		Rademakers	Netherlands

299		McKenna	Ireland
300	WHO Regional Office for Europe	Sørensen	Who European Region
301	WHO Regional Office for Europe		Who European Region
302		Okan	Who European Region
303	WHO Regional Office for Europe	Rowlands	Who European Region
304		Brach	USA
305		Van der Doelen	Netherlands
306		Lo	Australia
307		Beauchamp	Australia
308		Noordman	Netherlands
309		Zanobin	Italy
310		O'Connell	UK
311		Lexén	Sweden
312		Peyton	Australia
313		Peyton	Australia
314		Nobre	Portugal
315		Yulianti	Indonesia
316		Kusaka	Japan
317		Moroni	Australia
318		Aida	Japan
319		Shnaigat	Australia
320		Hosseinzadeh	Australia
321		Visscher	Netherlands
322		Ridout	Australia
323		Patafio	Australia
324		Fretjan	Germany
325	Who European Region	Bakker	Europe
326		Rowsell	UK
327	UNICEF, The Lancet and Financial Times Commission		Various
328		Baccolini	Croatia
329		Baccolini	Czechia
330		Baccolini	Denmark

331		Baccolini	Sweden
332		Baccolini	Finland
333		Baccolini	France
334		Baccolini	Germany
335		Baccolini	Greece
336		Baccolini	Hungary
337		Baccolini	Ireland
338		Baccolini	Italy
339		Baccolini	Lithuania
340		Baccolini	Netherlands
341		Baccolini	Poland
342		Baccolini	Portugal
343		Baccolini	Spain
344		Nawabi	Austria
345		Nawabi	Croatia
346		Nawabi	Finland
347		Nawabi	France
348		Nawabi	Ireland
349		Nawabi	Italy
350		Nawabi	Netherlands
351		Nawabi	Poland
352		Nawabi	Slovenia
353		Nawabi	Sweden
354		Nawabi	Canada
355		Nawabi	Turkey
356		Nawabi	USA
357		Nawabi	Norway
358		Nawabi	Iceland
359		Nawabi	Russia
360		Nawabi	Serbia
361		Nawabi	Switzerland
362		Nawabi	UK
363		Rowlands	Austria
364		Rowlands	Belgium
365		Rowlands	Bulgaria
366		Rowlands	Croatia
367		Rowlands	Cyprus
368		Rowlands	Czechia

369		Rowlands	Denmark
370		Rowlands	Estonia
371		Rowlands	Finland
372		Rowlands	France
373		Rowlands	Germany
374		Rowlands	Hungary
375		Rowlands	Ireland
376		Rowlands	Italy
377		Rowlands	Latvia
378		Rowlands	Lithuania
379		Rowlands	Luxembourg
380		Rowlands	Malta
381		Rowlands	Netherlands
382		Rowlands	Poland
383		Rowlands	Portugal
384		Rowlands	Romania
385		Rowlands	Slovakia
386		Rowlands	Slovenia
387		Rowlands	Spain
388		Rowlands	Sweden
389			UK
390	The Good Things Foundation		UK
391		Richardson	USA
392	Welsh Government		Wales
393	NIHR, National Institute for Health and Care Research	Faluyi	UK
394	Alberta Government		Canada
395	Victoria Government		Australia
396			USA
397		Bale	Australia
398	UOC eHealth Center, Behavioural Design Lab	Hernández	Spain
399	University of Cádiz-Faculty of Nursing and Physiotherapy	Bas-Sarmiento	Spain
400	University of Cádiz-Faculty of Nursing and Physiotherapy		Spain
401	University of Cádiz-Faculty of Nursing and Physiotherapy	Correro-Bermejo	Spain
402	Cosmo-Spain	Falcón	Spain
403	Asociación DIPEX Spain		Spain
404	Gobierno de Canarias	Perestelo-Perez	Spain
405	Col·legi Oficial d'Infermeres i Infermers de Barcelona		Spain

ANNEX III. REFERENCE REPOSITORY DATASET

1.
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ANNEX IV. LANDING PAGE IDEAHL GALH WEBPAGE

Banner Image

Indicate which image you would like to use and where it's located in your image folder. Banner image should be high resolution (at least 1920px wide and 450px high). Images without faces are preferred due to cropping.

digitalhealth-masthead-1920x450px.jpg.

Intro text

A single sentence that captures the key aspects.

The Global Atlas of Literacies for Health (GALH) is an online visualisation tool for teaching, research, practice and policy making in health care.

Extended Intro/About

A short paragraph or two capturing the core of your research.

The Global Atlas of Literacies for Health is a resource that not only summarises the various literacy instruments but presents the empirical evidence for how the tools have been used or evaluated and best practice in (d)HL across Europe and beyond.

The Atlas is:

- an online data visualisation tool that shows the levels of (digital) health literacy, best practice, policy, interventions and initiatives in Europe and beyond developed and managed by RMIT University based on the results of the European Union-funded IDEAHL project.
- a comprehensive resource for (d)HL policymaking in the EU
- a tool for enhancing teaching, research, practice and policy in health care
- a resource for promoting health equity and digital empowerment in the EU and beyond

The Atlas was developed to visually present the data from different (d)HL scales, best practice, policy, interventions and initiatives on an interactive map. Users can filter data by population: adult, child and adolescence, health workforce, or select to present only country or region level data.

It is part of the project called Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL, <https://ideahl.eu/>) that has received funding by the Horizon Europe Framework Program under GA 101057477. (See Buhl Povlsen M, Brun Thorup C, Schack Thoft D, Korsbakke Emtekær Hæsum L, Valkama K, Uitto M, et al. D1.1. Report on (d)HL WP1 . IDEAHL; https://ideahl.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/IDEAHL_D1.1.-Report-on-dHL.pdf)

The Atlas is open access, free of charge and can be accessed via your web browser at

ENTER

How to cite: Digital Health Hub RMIT University. The Global Atlas of Literacies for Health. 2023. Barcelona: RMIT Europe/IDEAHL Project funded by the EU. Available at: www.rmit.eu

(IMAGE IDEAHL EU FUNDED)

Disclaimer. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Key Research Areas:

Up to eight key areas with no more than 25 words describing them. Try to keep them all relatively equal in length. (This section can be expanded on a child page if needed)

Health literacy, digital health literacy, healthcare, digital health, public health

Feature Project/s

Up to four key projects with no more than 50 words describing them. Try to keep them all relatively equal in length. (This section can be expanded on a child page if needed)

Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL)

IDEAHL is a coordination and support action financed by Horizon Europe. Its purpose is to develop and test new models and approaches of digital health literacy ((d)HL) intervention development and application through the co-creation of a comprehensive and inclusive EU digital health literacy strategy. Its ultimate purpose is the empowerment of EU citizens in using digital tools to take a more active role in the management of their own health.

The project's results can be downloaded at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057477/results/es>

IDEAHL is a Consortium of 14 organisations (see Consortium - IDEAHL) and is coordinated by CONSEJERIA DE SALUD – PRINCIPADO DE ASTURIAS (<https://www.astursalud.es/astursalud>)

Contact details:

What's the best way for your audience to reach you? Do you have an active Social Media presence you would like people to follow? (Note – this information will be publicly available)

<https://www.rmit.edu.au/partner/hubs/digital-health-hub>
digital.health.hub@rmit.edu.au

ANNEX V. FAQs in GALH WEBSITE

Which are the information sources of the GALH?

The information sources considered for the GALH come from the IDEAHL scoping reviews conducted from 2017 to July 2023 and include:

- (1) Published articles based on research in HL and dHL,
- (2) non-academic works and initiatives,
- (3) key EU policies and (4) projects/EU Projects.

The Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living (IDEAHL 2023) project identified models and approaches of (digital) health literacy. The project first extracted relevant literature from 2017-2022 that published the literacy rate using the various tools across Europe, and country level documents about best practice, policy, interventions and initiatives were generated.

The objectives of the review were to map EU (d)HL research to assess the interconnections between (d)HL contribution and health, healthy living, and the well-being of citizens, to Map (d)HL practices and identify best practices, and champions and to review existing monitoring mechanisms and indicators and synthesize data to assess EU (d)HL levels. (See: Buhl Povlsen M, Brun Thorup C, Schack Thoft D, Korsbakke Emtækær Hæsum L, Valkama K, Uitto M, et al. D1.1. Report on (d)HL WP1 . IDEAHL; https://ideahl.eu/content/uploads/2023/03/IDEAHL_D1.1.-Report-on-dHL.pdf)

What data is available in the GALH of the IDEAHL project?

The data available comes from the information sources of the GALH and includes the following categories.

For monitoring levels of digital health literacy (dHL) and health literacy: country, population, scale, first author, country coverage, HL or dHL, reference, note

For best practice, policy, interventions, projects and initiatives: country, year, title, lead organisation, status, international/national/regional, public or private, type (report, book,

dissertation, project, website, etc.), HL, dHL, other, age group, target group, level (individual, family, community, group, society, organisational), sector (academia, education, industry, public health), tool or scale, champion/survivor, reference, note.

What is a SCALE and how does it work?

Scales refer to monitoring and evaluation tools, methods, and frameworks in (d)HL that are validated and published in peer-reviewed journals; they measure/quantify individuals' (d)HL and organisations' HL and (d)HL environments covering different target populations and services (e.g., the HLS-EU questionnaire, the eHL Assessment toolkit -eHLA- and the eHL Questionnaire -eHLQ-, HLQ, BRIEF, etc). A health literacy scale is a standardised questionnaire or survey designed to capture various aspects of health literacy, such as the ability to understand and use health information, navigate healthcare systems, and make informed decisions about health. These scales typically consist of a series of questions or statements that respondents rate or respond to, providing quantitative data on their health literacy abilities. Health literacy scales are valuable in research, evaluation, and intervention efforts, helping to identify gaps, track progress and tailor interventions to improve health literacy and promote better health outcomes. The GALH compiles different types of scales that measure (d)HL. To see a complete description of the scale and how it is implemented you could either see the reference and read the study where it was applied or visit the [Health Literacy Tool Shed \(bu.edu\)](https://bu.edu/HealthLiteracyToolShed) (Boston University, 2023) where you can find detailed information on HL scales.

How can the GALH be used?

Data from the GALH can be used to build interactive map views. These can be exported , used and shared across a range of channels including new publications, reports, conferences, workshops and teaching activities, websites and social media. The aim of the GALH is to be widely used in teaching, research and policymaking in healthcare.

Who can use the GALH?

The GALH can be used by educators, researchers, policy makers, practitioners, civil society and patient organisations, and citizens who have an interest in the field of (d)HL.

Understanding trends in different literacy scales for a region can inform scholarly teaching needs, research and policy making, health care patient needs and citizens. Different literacy needs can

be targeted in curriculum and research development, health programs, policy and care depending on the discipline and regional needs. In the area of health, it is important to not only develop the health and digital literacy rates knowledge in general but to clearly understand the literacy rates of the different target populations that will eventually receive treatment and care and be subject of policies and interventions. Yet, there are over one hundred different literacy tools available, as shown in the Health Literacy Tool Shed (Boston University 2023, Health Literacy Tool Shed (bu.edu)). The GALH, then, is developed as tool that not only summarises the various literacy scales but presents the empirical evidence for how they have been used or evaluated in different geographical regions, best practice, interventions and initiatives so that the users can understand and evaluate.

How can I access the GALH?

The GALH of the IDEAHL project is open access, free of charge and can be accessed via your web browser at: www.rmit.eu/galh